

The EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence¹

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Abstract:

In 2022, EU leaders identified space as a strategic domain in the Strategic Compass and called for an EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence. In a joint endeavour between the European Commission and the High Representative, the first EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence (SSSD) was published in 2023. The Strategy establishes a foundation for a shared understanding of space threats among EU Member States and enhancing the resilience and protection of space systems and services of the EU. It outlines measures for responding to space threats, strengthening the use of space for security and defence, and promoting partnerships to encourage responsible behaviour in space. This article explores the development of the SSSD and the EU's recognition of space as a strategic domain, outlining its main pillars and reporting on the current state of implementation. Moreover, it explores the evolving role and growing significance of a coherent EU space strategy amid changing geopolitical dynamics.

Keywords:

EU Space Policy; Space Strategy; Strategic Compass; Space Security and Defence; Space Threats; Space Diplomacy

1. Introduction

Space services have become indispensable and integral to the daily functioning of our societies and economies. At the same time, space has always involved a security and defence dimension. Space is a critical enabler of modern warfare, providing vital intelligence and situational awareness capabilities that allow for near real-time tracking of troop movements and manoeuvres, precision guidance, as well as communications services. These are crucial for ensuring swift and coordinated military responses on the battlefield: The Ukrainian army, for example, in its continued fight against Russia's war of aggression makes extensive and decisive use of space systems every day.

As space is becoming more and more essential, space systems and services also become targets. Over the recent decades, the number of space threats has intensified significantly. Several nations have developed so-called counter space capabilities, which cover a range of abilities for disrupting, degrading, destroying, or denying the use of space systems.

Space is now regarded as a strategic domain. In 2019, the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) for the first time recognized space as its fifth operational domain, next to air, land, maritime, and cyberspace. Following several discussions among EU leaders, the EU Strategic

¹ This article is the abstract of the presentation delivered on 28 November 2024 at the Hellenic Air Force Academy, as part of the Common Module on Space Applications for Security and Defence 2024. The event was organised under the auspices of the European Security and Defence College (ESDC) of the European Union.

Compass,¹ formally approved by the EU and its Member States in March 2022, also referred to Space as strategic domains and called for a European Union Space Strategy for Security and Defence (SSSD).

A few months later, in the eve of the Russian invasion, a number of threats in the space domain became reality: A major SatCom infrastructure was cyber-attacked by Russia, and the supply of launchers and other key components of the EU space programmes became more difficult. A few years after having destroyed one of their own satellites with an anti-satellite missile back in November 2021, a test which was widely condemned, Russia started to publicly declare threaten commercial satellites used by Ukraine to defend itself.

2. The Genesis of Space Strategy for Space Security & Defence

The preparation of the EU Space Strategy for Space Security & Defence mobilized a lot of relevant actors across EU institutions and Member States. In its format of a Joint Communication, the SSSD was a joint endeavour between the European External Action Service (EEAS) serving the High Representative for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy and the Directorate General for Defence Industry and Space (DG DEFIS) of the European Commission. Further expertise was supplied by the European Defence Agency (EDA) as well as the European Union Military Staff (EUMS). The EU Member States were involved throughout the entire process through a series of informal consultation workshops, briefings as well as bilateral exchanges. Consultations of the space industry, think tanks, and academia also provided very useful inputs.

Few months after the Joint Communication on the SSSD was adopted the Council adopted Conclusion and the European adopted a Reports both of which were very supportive to the proposed action of the strategy.²

2.1 Understanding Space Threats

The first element of the SSSD addresses the scope and what we understand as ‘space domain’ which “*includes any element relevant for the functioning of space systems and the delivery of space-based services in the EU and the Member States*”. Importantly, this definition not only encompasses the space environment and space-based assets such as satellites, but also ground facilities, radio frequency links, user terminals, as well as the industrial space sector and their underlying supply chains.

The first actions envisaged in the strategy relate to awareness and the need to develop a strategic culture of space security across Europe. The SSSD emphasises the importance of a shared understanding of space threats. The EU now provides an annual, classified analysis of the space threat developments based on the intelligence contributions by the EU Member States.

2.2 Increasing the resilience of the European Space sector

The SSSD then addresses the need to increase the resilience and the protection of space systems delivering services to the EU. This goes beyond the systems and services of the EU Space Programme, such as the Galileo navigation system and the Copernicus earth observation system: The European Commission and its EU Agency for the Space Programme is working with the EU industrial space sector to increase both security awareness and the exchange of best practices through so-called Information Security Awareness Centres (ISACs). The Commission is also preparing a new European Space Act to shape a European internal market of space systems and services, with a view to ensure a level playing field for security, sustainability, and resilience across the EU.

2.3 Responding to Space Threats

The EU also needs to deter others from threatening the EU and its Member States' space systems and services. To this end, the SSSD proposes to further develop the EU Space Threat Response Architecture originally established to ensure security of systems and services deployed, operated and used under the Union Space Programme which may affect the security of the Union. The High Representative will propose to amend the existing legal framework, to ensure an even more thorough and swift EU-level reaction to a wider range of space threats through a toolbox for countering space threats using diplomatic, technical, economic, and potentially military responses. Such a mechanism would complement and interoperate with the already existent cyber diplomacy and hybrid toolboxes. The EU regularly exercises its response to space threats along with the mutual defence clause (Article 42.7 TFUE), in case a space incident would amount to an armed aggression on the territory of a Member State.

2.4 Enhancing the use of space for security and defence

The SSSD also addresses the need to make better use of the space systems and services for security and defence. This includes capabilities such as Galileo's Public Regulated Service (PRS) for military-grade positioning and timing, a strategic enabler for military operations, or how sensor development can support the national Space Domain Awareness capabilities of our Member States. The new flagship IRIS², which will provide secure and highly resilient communications to Member State governments, is set to become fully operational by 2030. Meanwhile, the GovSatCom component of the EU Space Programme already helps with the pooling and sharing of Governmental Satellite Communication capabilities of EU Member States.

Earth Observation is also essential for security and defence: Copernicus is a success story of the European Space programme but its main purpose relates to environmental monitoring and climate change. The SSSD now calls for the establishment of a dedicated EU Earth Observation Governmental Service (EOGS) in order to ensure a highly resilient and continuously available situational awareness service in support of high-end security and defence applications. This new capability would help increase the strategic autonomy of SatCen, the EU's geospatial intelligence centre, our eyes in orbit in support of the EU's common security, defence and foreign policy CFSP and CSDP.

2.5 External engagement

Finally, the SSSD highlights the essential role of partnerships to ensure responsible behaviour in space. The EU is committed to preventing an arms race in outer space both because it would prevent the use of space for future generation and because it could dangerously amplify tensions, given the strategic nature of space. The EU, as permanent observer in the United Nations (UN) supports its Member States in relevant discussions, particularly in the newly established Open-Ended Working Group on Preventing an Arms Race in Outer Space. The EU frequently addresses space security issues as part of dedicated EU dialogues with third countries. Such dialogues help coordinate efforts with our partners and allies, share our vision of peaceful uses of outer space, and the establishment of relevant diplomatic channels to avoid miscalculation.

NATO is an essential partner. In December 2023, the EU and NATO launched a Structured Dialogue to explore cooperation in areas including space security, the need for education and training, as well as responsible space behaviours.

3. Conclusion

Since the adoption of the SSSD in 2023, the geopolitical context has considerably evolved and the risks did not decrease. For the first time since the adoption of the Outer Space Treaty, a resolution on space security was brought to the attention of the UN Security Council, reminding us of the risks posed by the possible deployment of nuclear weapons in space.

In this context the reports of the Sauli Niinistö on Strengthening the Europe's Civilian and Military Preparedness of 2024,³ as well as of Mario Draghi on the Future of European Competitiveness in September 2024 refer to the importance of Space.⁴

To implement all of the above action, Europe needs to revisit its approach of space cooperation. We need to train and educate our workforce and industry in space security and defence, enable the EU to protect its interests, reduce dependency on external partners, and strengthen our strategic autonomy in an increasingly competitive global landscape.

References

¹ Council of the European Union, "A Strategic Compass for Security and Defence - For a European Union that Protects its Citizens, Values and Interests and Contributes to International Peace and Security", 2022. Available:

<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-7371-2022-INIT/en/pdf>

² European Commission and High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, "Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council on the European Union Space Strategy for Security and Defence," JOIN(2023) 9 final, Brussels, 2023

³ Niinistö, Sauli. Safer Together: Strengthening Europe's Civilian and Military Preparedness and Readiness. European Commission, 30 Oct. 2024,

https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/5bb2881f-9e29-42f2-8b77-8739b19d047c_en?filename=2024_Niinisto-report_Book_VF.pdf.

⁴ Draghi, Mario. The Future of European Competitiveness. European Commission, 9 Sept. 2024, https://commission.europa.eu/topics/eu-competitiveness/draghi-report_en.

Short Biography:

Patrick Chatard Moulin is Senior Adviser on Space Security and Defence at the European External Action Service (EEAS), focusing on space security, defence, and international aspects of European Space Policy. With 15 years of EU experience, he has worked on initiatives such as Space Surveillance, GOVSATCOM, and EU SatCen. He joined the European Defence Agency in 2005, launching cooperative projects, before serving in the EU's General Secretariat of the Council and DG GROW's Space Policy unit. From 2017 to 2021, he oversaw EUROSUR and contributed to drafting the European Border and Coast Guard Regulation at DG HOME. A former French Air Force Engineering Officer with over 15 years of service, Patrick graduated from the French Air Force Academy and Telecom Paris as a SATCOM Engineer. He is an International Space University alumnus and guest lecturer.